

The Armed Forces in Future Conflicts

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In the imaginable future plausible conflicts are unlikely to occur in prolonged ground campaigns, with major inconclusive battles and lengthy periods of immobility and slow destruction, on large, well-defined fronts.

Although battles and periods of attrition have occurred in the war between Iran and Iraq (countries that have been able to sustain them for a long time - a model of war whose repetition is not impossible but unlikely), in the Gulf conflicts - 1991 was an intervention with limited objectives, without total defeat, the Balkans - 1999 and Afghanistan - 2001/2002, (which took place under a now more credible model, that of asymmetric intervention), action on land it was characterized by rapid penetration and / or flanking or even manoeuvring in limited zones rather than battle fronts, after the enemy ground force's operational capacity was reduced by air strikes, missiles and special operations.

There is at all any similarly with the large units of heavy (armoured), heavy artillery and conventional infantry very influential in the most relevant conventional land theatres in the 20th century (Europe, North Africa, First and Second World Wars).

The collapse of the Iraqi Army in 1991, the effective survival of these large units, with their supportive all-round paraphernalia, is compromised by the lethal accuracy and efficiency of modern weapons - aviation (airplanes and helicopters) and cruise missiles.

Although, still present in the great powers and in some countries with classic regional concerns and cares (Korea, Iraq itself, Israel and a few others), in general the large heavy units are no longer the "flagship" of the Modern armies.

Countries, which are at least relevant in their geopolitical region, should have these tanks, although in smaller relative dimensions than in the past, as restricted or occasional situations may arise where their shock power is convenient.

The trend is that the importance of short-term, ready-to-deploy ground forces (repeating, strategic and operational-tactical deployment), ready for the modern-style "blitzkrieg" with heavy use of helicopters and special operations is growing in importance (destruction / sabotage, seizure, recognition and attainment of "intelligence", hostage or non-combatant rescue and counterterrorism), well endowed with weapons, communications, sensors and other technologically advanced equipment.

These forces, structured into moderated sized operating units are deployed for restricted and localized and / or limited purpose purposes in non-urban as well as

urban areas, with their close-range, high-risk combat for the local population (which requires special training), operating more or less carefully or isolated, with initiative but in complete coordination.

Depending on the presumed role of each army and in accordance with their respective national strategic problems, additional units suitable for territorial control can be added.

Modern armies are expensive, which contraindicates its distribution of over large territory, being replaced with its the presence provided by mobility.

All of this means smaller, more professional, more technologies, more expensive, and of course less grounded armies in the obligatory universal conscription of the old mass armies endowed with slow obsolescence weapons, less demanding of skill to use and maintain them – still a trend in countries that depend on armies for internal political control.

As for the sea, long campaigns with extensive maritime battles (maritime area control) similar to those in the Pacific (between the United States and Japan, major air battles), and campaigns of attrition or denial of sea use will also be unlikely.

Such campaigns did not even happen in the major post-WWII conflicts (Korea, Vietnam, Gulf, Balkans, Afghanistan), in which the oceanic support was never threatened.

An exception could have been the Falklands conflict in 1982 if Argentina had relied on some reconnaissance-backed submarines capable of unbalancing the umbilical cord of the projection of English power, essentially maritime.

The broad domain of the sea in its traditional sense was not the purpose of the Russian Federation fleets, except in waters within its reach.

Airplanes flying from the coast controlled by it (defensive strategy) and for the short strictly necessary time - even because it would be impracticable to prolong it given the American supremacy at sea, in the exit areas of its submarines, from the restricted seas in which they were located the bases in the Arctic and Siberia coasts to the Atlantic and Pacific.

The maritime domain, once again in its classic sense, has no rational purpose in limited and short regional conflicts, where sea care naturally comes down to coastal defense.

Transoceanic traffic lacks vital strategic importance for the resolution of such conflicts, and is unlikely and objectively illogical for countries of a regional nature to develop and

sustain expensive and complex naval conditions for conducting oceanic campaigns in a contribution to conflict resolution.

The US Navy tends today to focus less on blue (distant ocean) and non-distant (coastal) waters, with one caution: the emphasis is on enemy coastal waters (offensive strategy) rather than its own (defensive strategy).).

They therefore tend to emphasize the strategy of projecting sea power and attacking land targets and supporting ground operations, amphibious landing, logistic support to ground forces rather than the strategy at sea, an emphasis that the assumption of safe use of blue water.

This assumption is natural to US Navy because it is capable of quickly restoring security, if any cyclical or eventual threaten.

For the United States, the oceans, which were the protective barrier of its developmental and democratic isolationism in the 19th century (a protection similar to that which had favoured England in the turbulent European scenario), and simultaneously the protective barrier and transit theatre of its projection of power in the 20th century, they tend to be mainly the latter in the 21st century, of US naval hegemony and of no expressive naval threat to the United States.

Onboard aircrafts, in evidence for the last seventy years, is a weapon system for typical navy operations with extensive and / or distant charges or responsibilities.

It was never intended in any country for the close defense of what is conventionally called the maritime border line - a flexible geographical concept given the possibility of projecting sea power inland beyond the shoreline, but commonly understood to encompass the coastal waters with their traffic, other interests in them and the coastline itself.

In such cases, the air contribution is feasible by flying from land without exposing the aircraft carrier. In the United States, the use of airplanes in the routine control of coastal waters - maritime illicit control, safety and rescue - is assigned to Coast Guard aircraft, and the defense of the warring coastline, Air Force and / or Navy aircraft flying from earth.

This conception of employment is not emphasized in American strategic policy.

China needs this weapon system as it intends to extend its hegemony at sea beyond the reach of land-based airforce in the western Pacific and the South China Sea.

This issue, actually, would be a challenge to the United States, unnecessary for its current goals.

Air operations are important in interventions and sometimes even essential if there are no convenient located air bases available on land, or if, given the political-strategic circumstances of the problem, pre-positioning of intervention forces near the target, but not on the territory of any country, for short-term employment.

Pre-positioning obviously it is not subject to legal disputes if carried out in international waters.

If there is an aerial threat to the aircraft carrier, part of its aircraft must serve its own defense.

This situation is not plausible in intervention conflicts, since the target countries are generally unable to act expressively at sea, if at all, even small, always vulnerable to the intervening higher power.

Also because technology allow a discreet complementation - of missile aircraft to be replaced in attack missions, such as the Tomahawk launched from the Persian Gulf and the Indian missiles over Iraq and Afghanistan. .

Technology allows a planned missions to target pre-defined targets to be carried out from very distant bases of uncontroversial use.

Regarding the safety of ocean traffic, the criticism stems from the fact that in the near future imaginable, conflicts are unlikely to pose such a threat to maritime transport, the reason being the small aircraft carriers of the past, nucleus of anti-task force groups.

The submarine as well as threat eventually practiced by naval / naval force capable of requiring the intervention of interception and attack aircraft embarked on larger aircraft carriers.

This argument is certainly less valid for the United States, a power that guarantees tranquillity in the oceans, for which it may be exceptionally necessary to use the potential of its aircraft carriers to restore security by chance in some threatened maritime region.

This hypothesis is indeed very unlikely, but not at all impossible, in a short-term economic situation.

Surface ships are still useful for various types of mission: patrol, blockade, ground projection, cannon and missiles, and even escort in special circumstances.

Ships with Tomahawk-type missiles do not quite mean what large aircraft carriers with their planes mean today in power projection over land, but they complement and tend to gradually replace them in various situations, with the evolution of technology involved.

This trend is at the heart of the American design of the future arsenal ship capable of providing efficient missile action on strategic and operational targets on land.

Submarines, now also armed with missiles as well as torpedoes, are the best weapon for action against superior naval forces - and will continue to be until technology has put a decisive end to its stealth (it is already reducing it).

They are suitable for any mission where discretion is required, but their classic mission, exhausted by the Germans in the Atlantic and the Americans in the Pacific, in World War II - the attack on maritime traffic that threatened survival. England and completely undermined that of Japan, island countries drastically dependent on maritime support.

Amphibious projection is also feasible and often convenient in the quick raid, performed by small units with restricted purposes, such as taking a port or airport and temporarily protecting the landing of larger forces, beyond those for special operations: destruction of sabotage, attack, recognition and obtaining of "intelligence", rescue of hostages or non-combatants and counterterrorism.

Recognizing the importance of these operations in the now more likely conflict scenarios, the US Navy has already adapted submarines to conduct discrete operations with special Marine units.

Today and in the imaginable future, the use of aircraft in attack missions is particularly suited for two types of action:

- First, the establishment of the local air superiority necessary for effective and safe ground action, a problem that may require the sometimes politically complicated initiative, with air base aimed to destroy ground support and enemy ground aviation itself, airspace control and air operations facilities, and air defense facilities.

- Second, simultaneous or sequential to the first, the preparation for ground support for ground operation, with attacks on targets influential in enemy capability, in the operational and logistical spheres: ground combat interdiction, attacks on defensive positions, to "intelligence", command and communication centres, military depots, force concentrations, means of transport, etc.

When urban targets such as command centers, communications, transportation, TV stations have to be attacked, human and technical errors commonly produce destruction and unwanted deaths.

Attacks by UAV's or conventional aircrafts, equipped with "smart" weapons, complemented by missiles launched from land or sea, lead to the suggestion that they resolve the conflict.

In fact, what it does facilitate the final solution necessarily produced by action "on the ground" and reduce its risks.

Its success depends on two requirements:

- High technological and willingness are required, and
- material / logistical, psychosocial and financial conditions to maintain the expensive and complex effort.

High-tech weapon systems are decisively effective when their use has significant effects on the target country with some military, infrastructural and economic sophistication.

In guerrilla war and other unconventional operations or so-called low intensity conflicts are less profitable; There are regions that are far behind or of geophysical characteristics unfavourable to the effectiveness of such weapons.

Guerrilla warfare, involving regular and / or irregular forces, rarely has regular forces on both sides in different situations.

It is a modality of prolonged attrition, still plausible where there are conditions that facilitate it: geophysical (jungle, mountains), socioeconomic and psycho political (underdevelopment, epidemic poverty, precarious infrastructure, mobilizing ideology and even criminal motivations, if not combination).

These conditions commonly hinder the manoeuvring of classical ground forces, which are less agile than those of the guerrilla, and, as noted above, undermine the effectiveness of technological asymmetry favourable to regular forces.

In guerrilla conflicts, the distinction between combatants and non-combatants is blurred, as well as between, on the one hand, something that could be admitted close to the classical concept of war (with its more or less protective formal or customary conventions of the people) and of the combatants themselves, and the diffuse and confusing combat between legal forces and illegal forces eventually associated with criminality.

This type of combat, particularly when criminals intervene or inspire, sometimes approaches the mere confrontation between military forces acting as police and the "outlaws" - reduces the possibility of ethical and legal controls.

Moreover, there are no well-defined fronts on them, but inaccurate combat areas. Guerrilla forces very rarely defend defined objectives and use space and time to avoid direct confrontation.

Its operations are characterized by initiative and stealth and agile manoeuvre, with punctual attacks that disturb and / or immobilize the adversary involved in protection and defense commitments, whether urban, communications and transport lines, command centers, control and logistics or others.

Guerrilla warfare - whose success or failure is measured more by its longer-term political outcome than by the immediate military, is decided not only in combat, but also in theatrical advertising can have offensive purposes, often changing the political and social order, or defensive.

Such purposes becomes operational fundamentally by the diffuse but constant harassment and the control exerted by the regular forces; if sustained for a long time, this harassment can lead the enemy to moderate his goals or to give them up.

The armed forces suitable for the guerrilla warfare are not exactly the ones that are used to confront organized state forces, but are a subject matter to the injunctions already made about the suitability of very high-tech weapons systems. The convenient military configuration depends on the geophysical, psychosocial characteristics and level of infrastructure development of the region concerned.

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